

RD4 is a short-stawed, early variety from the cross LT/IR8//W1252///RD2. & was intended as a stopgap measure for Farmers in areas of heavy gall midge infestation (in parts of the north and northeast, gall midge losses of as much as 75% occur frequently). A major complaint against RD4 has been its poor eating quality due to high gelatinization temperature which is not typical of the local varieties. RD4 is expected to make inroads in localities where gall midge is severe.

RD5 (PN 16/Sigadis) was the first attempt to produce an intermediate-height, stiff-stawed, late-maturing variety especially adapted to semideep water conditions of the central plain in the monsoon season. It is popular where farmers do not have water control and where bacterial blight is a problem. It is not as responsive to nitrogen as RD1, but farmers have reported yields of 5.6 t/ha. RD5 also shows promise

under the rainfed lowland conditions of the northeast, apparently due to some drought tolerance.

Although only released in 1975, RD7 (C4-63/GR88//Sigadis) appears to be spreading almost as rapidly as RD1 did in its earlier years. Farmers prefer it to RD1 because of its good cooking quality, resistance to bacterial blight, and showy panicles which resemble those of C4-63. It also promises to become popular in the southern region because of good panicle exertion and disease resistance. RD7 is the first RD variety with intermediate amylose content.

The threat of an outbreak of brown planthopper and the need for a gall-midge-resistant, nonglutinous variety prompted the release of RD9 (LY34/TN1//W1256///RD2). Nonwaxy rice is preferred in areas on the east coast of Thailand where gall midge is endemic.

The diffusion of genetic materials among rice breeders in India

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Through analysis of breeding records and in-depth interviews, we traced the flow of rice genetic materials among collaborating Indian research stations through three periods over a decade: 1965–67, 1970–71, and 1974–75. We also determined breeding objectives of 1974–75 crosses as part of a collaborative project with the Agricultural Education Department of Iowa State University, U.S.A. We randomly selected and analyzed 44 crosses from the 1965–67 breeding records and 68 crosses from the 1970–71 records at seven state- and national-level research centers. For 1974–75, we analyzed 44 crosses made at 10 centers.

We found that 82 percent of the 1965–67 crosses involved at least one semidwarf parent. TN1 was used in 41 percent of the crosses; IR8, in 27 percent; and IRRI rices other than IR8, in 14 percent (see figure). No locally developed semidwarfs were found in the 1965–67 sample. The percentage of total crosses that involved semidwarfs increased to 91 percent in 1970–71 and leveled off through 1974–75. By the early 1970's, the direct use of TN1 as a parent in crosses had dropped to 10 percent, and to 7 percent by 1974–75. The use of IR8 as a parent dropped 1 percent over the first 5 years, then dropped to 17 percent by 1974–75. The use of semidwarf materials from other countries increased slightly.

While other IRRI materials were used increasingly by 1974–75, locally developed semidwarfs were even more popular. They were used in almost half of the crosses by 1970–71 and in 61 percent by 1974–75. Fifty-five percent of local semidwarfs used in 1974–75 were progenies of IR8 and 39 percent, of TN1 (9 percent involved both) (see figure). Seventy-seven percent of the crosses in 1965–67 involved a tall parent, but only 48 percent did in 1974–75. The use of intermediate-statured parents declined from 45 percent in 1965–67 to 18 percent in 1974–75. Seventy-nine percent

a) Indian rice breeders used Taichung Native 1 and IR8 intensively in the mid-1960's, but they had largely switched to locally developed semidwarfs and improved IRRI lines by 1974–75.

b) Ninety-four percent of the local semidwarfs were progeny of IR8 or TN1. Analysis of 336 rices used as parents in 158 randomly selected crosses, 10 experiment stations, India, 1975.

of the total parent material was indica in the mid-1960's; 10 years later, 96 percent was indica. The use of japonicas and ponlais declined over the decade.

Fifty-seven percent of the total parents were hybrids in 1965-67, and 74 percent in 1974-75.

Thus, we conclude that by the mid-1970's the original stiff-strawed varieties were being phased out of the breeding programs as parents, but that they continued to live on through a wide range of progeny. Rice breeders have incorporated their best genetic traits into newer rices better suited to local conditions.

Objectives of rice breeders in India

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To determine the overall objectives of rice breeders, we interviewed rice breeders at 10 agricultural research centers in India. We compiled the genetic traits for which the breeders used each parent

in each of 46 randomly selected crosses made in 1974-75.

Yield potential was cited as a primary breeding objective for making 89 percent of the crosses; fertilizer response was a breeding objective of 80 percent; and resistance to lodging, of 80 percent (see figure). Semidwarfs were almost invariably used as genetic sources of these traits. Grain quality was an objective of 69 percent of the crosses. Seventy-three percent of the times that tall varieties were used, the breeders hoped to transfer a preferred type of grain into the progeny; semidwarfs were used only 49 percent of the time for that. We found that 82 percent of the semidwarfs used for grain quality were locally developed, further indicating that introduced semidwarfs were often crossed with local rices to develop high-yielding varieties with acceptable grain quality. Forty-three percent of the crosses involved resistance to at least one disease, and 37 percent involved insect resistance. Resistance to blast, bacterial blight, and tungro virus were the most frequent disease objectives. Brown planthopper and gall midge

resistance were the most common insect objectives. Drought tolerance was sought in 9% of the crosses; cold tolerance, in 9%; tolerance to waterlogged soils, in 7%; and tolerance to deep water, in 2%. Tall or intermediate-statured parents were used as donors for most of these traits.

Development and spread of high-yielding varieties of rice in Iran

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About 80 percent of Iran's 380,000 ha of rice is grown in the two Caspian littoral provinces of Gilan and Mazandaran, which have sub-Mediterranean (warm temperate) climates with humid summers and mild winters. The ricegrowing season is from mid-April to late September, during which the average maximum temperature is from 18° to 31°C and the minimum is from 8.2° to 20°C.

About 70 percent of the rice area is planted to long, fine-grained varieties of the Sadri type, such as Dumsiah, Dumzard, Dumsorkh, and Moosa Tarom. The Sadri varieties have very good cooking quality by Iranian standards: long, fine kernels that elongate considerably on boiling but do not tend to expand or burst. The cooked rice is tender and remains soft even if kept overnight. The remaining area is devoted to medium- and short-grained varieties known as the Champas. All are indicas and are tall, weak-stemmed, and leafy. Mutual shading and lodging are problems, particularly when the plants are fertilized. Mehr, Firooz, Dumzard 193, Moosa Tarom 110, and Dumsiah 81 are improved Sadri varieties developed by selection from local mixtures. They are not heavy yielders and are susceptible to blast disease. Some of the japonica varieties from Japan, Taiwan, Italy, Egypt, and other countries yielded from 7 to 9 t/ha in the International Rice Adaptation Trials in 1969, but they were acceptable to neither consumers nor farmers because they were short-grained, had poor cooking quality, and lacked seed dormancy (which is essential in Iran, where the harvest season generally coincides with the rainy season).

Increased yield potential was the major objective of rice breeders who made 46 randomly selected crosses in 1974-75. Fertilizer response and resistance to lodging also were important among their goals, as was improved grain quality. Ten agricultural experiment stations, India, 1975.